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Chemical Examination of the Leaves of

Rhus mysurensis

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THE present paper deals with the study of complex mixture of flavonoids in the leaves extract of *Rhus mysurensis* (Anacardiaceae) procured from the Government Botanical Garden, Ooty (India). While the work was in progress, Sarada and Adinarayana¹ reported the isolation of kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin, hinokiflavone and 3-*O*-rhamnosides of myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol from the leaves of the same species. Our investigations revealed the presence of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone in addition to hinokiflavone, quercetin and kaempferol besides quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside.

The acetone extract of defatted leaves of *R. mysurensis* showed four distinct spots on tlc examination (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5). They were labelled as RM-I to RM-IV and separated by preparative tlc (B-P-F).

RM-I, on methylation was found to be a mixture of three methyl ethers. The two methyl ethers, m.p. 228-29° and 302° were characterised as hexamethyl ethers of amentoflavone² and cupressuflavone³, respectively by their nmr spectral studies; the third methyl ether, m.p. 202°, could not be characterised due to paucity of material.

RM-II, on derivatisation gave a pentacetate, m.p. 240° and a methyl ether, m.p. 260°. It was characterised as hinokiflavone⁴ by comparison of nmr spectra of its acetate and methyl ether with that of an authentic sample. RM-III, m.p. 314°, and RM-IV, m.p. 278° were characterised as quercetin and kaempferol on the basis of uv and nmr spectral studies⁵.

The methanol extract of acetone exhausted leaves on tlc examination (ethyl acetate-ethyl methyl ketone-acetic acid-water, 5 : 3 : 1 : 1) showed three major brown spots under uv light. They were separated by preparative tlc and labelled as RMG-I to RMG-III. All the three compounds gave positive Molisch and Shinoda tests indicating all to be flavonoidic glycosides.

RMG-I, m.p. 231-33°, on acid hydrolysis gave quercetin (m.p. 314°) and glucose. Uv spectral studies of the glucoside showed attachment of the sugar at C-3-hydroxyl of the aglycone. The final confirmation of the sugar attachment was obtained by the identification of partial methyl ether (m.p. 193°) obtained on hydrolysis of methylated glycoside⁶. The RMG-I was therefore identified as quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside. Similarly, RMG-II, m.p. 181-83°, and RMG-III, m.p. 178°, were identified as quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside⁷, respectively.

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Occurrence of Aurentiacin in

Didymocarpus podocarpa

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PHYTOCHEMICAL investigation on two *Didymocarpus* species, *D. pedicellata* and *D. aurentiaca* led to the isolation of a number of chalcones¹, quinochalcones², flavanones³, terpenoids⁴ and α -pyrones⁵. Recently, three kaurenoid diterpenes have been reported from another *Didymocarpus* sp., *D. oblonga*⁶. Very recently, one α -pyrone derivative, 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain has also been found to occur in *D. podocarpa*⁷.

Extraction of the whole plant of *D. podocarpa* with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) led to the isolation of a compound, m.p. 141° which was crystallised as orange plates (petroleum ether-benzene) and